

A Study on Importance of Training in Tourism Industry in Madhya Pradesh

Paper Id : 18351 Submission Date : 14/12/2023 Acceptance Date : 22/12/2023 Publication Date : 25/12/2023

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10599187

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/shinkhlala.php#8>

Utasav Anand

Professor
Department Of Economics
Dr. Harisingh Gour
Vishwavidyalaya,
Sagar, Madhya Pradesh,
India

Archana Thakur

Research Scholar
Department Of Economics
Dr. Harisingh Gour
Vishwavidyalaya,
Sagar, Madhya Pradesh,
India

Abstract

This study examines the importance of training in the tourism industry in Madhya Pradesh, India. The tourism industry in Madhya Pradesh is a key contributor to the state's economy, and it is essential for organizations operating in the sector to invest in the professional development of their employees. The study explores the benefits of training for both employees and organizations in the hospitality industry, including improved skills and knowledge, increased job satisfaction, enhanced guest experience, increased revenue, improved productivity, and compliance with regulations. Data was collected through books, journal articles, and websites, and the findings indicate that training is critical for the success of the tourism industry in the state. The study concludes with recommendations for tourism organizations to invest in training programs for their employees to improve their skills, knowledge, and overall performance, leading to a better guest experience and increased profitability.

Keywords Tourism, Skills, Training and Development.

Introduction The tourism industry is one of the most significant contributors to the global economy, and Madhya Pradesh, a central state in India, is no exception. Madhya Pradesh is blessed with an abundance of natural beauty, cultural heritage, and historical significance. It is home to some of the country's most famous landmarks, such as the Khajuraho temples, the Sanchi stupa, and the ancient city of Mandu. As a result, the state has become a popular destination for tourists from around the world. To maintain and enhance the tourism industry's growth, it is essential to ensure that the industry workforce is well-trained and equipped with the necessary skills to provide a high-quality experience to tourists. The tourism industry is a service-based industry that depends on customer satisfaction, and this can only be achieved through skilled and knowledgeable employees. The importance of training in the tourism industry cannot be overstated. Training equips employees with the skills, knowledge, and attitudes necessary to provide excellent service to tourists. It helps them understand the nuances of customer service and how to communicate effectively with visitors. Moreover, training provides employees with the tools they need to deal with unforeseen circumstances, such as emergencies and difficult customers. In Madhya Pradesh, the tourism industry has been growing rapidly, and there is an increasing demand for well-trained professionals. The findings of this study will be useful for tourism industry stakeholders, including policymakers, tourism boards, and training institutes. The study will provide insights into the current state of training in the tourism industry in Madhya Pradesh.

Aim of study

1. To explore the training system in tourism industry in Madhya Pradesh.
2. To explore benefits of training in tourism industry in Madhya Pradesh.

Review of Literature

(Patil & Charantimath, 2021) conducted a study on "Employability through Skill Development Programmes - an overview of significance of Employability skills". Understanding the demand for employability skills and examining the gap between wanted and possessed skills were the study's main goals. The study found that training, education, and short-term courses can close the skill disparities. Despite the efforts, there is still much room for turning discarded knowledge into abilities. Together, we can

achieve the government of India's many lofty goals, such as Make in India, Atmanirbhar Bharat, and the 5-trillion-dollar economy ambitions.

(Banajawad & Adi, 2020) conducted a study on "A study on skill development programmes for rural youth in India" with the objective to ascertain the current status, challenges and the Government initiatives for the skill development in India. According to the study's findings, skill development is currently gaining speed, and it is now clear that education and skills are essential for improving employment prospects, reducing poverty, increasing productivity, and fostering ecologically sustainable rural development. Assimilation of rural development knowledge, policies, and tactics is necessary right away. It is essential to include industry-linked placement opportunities and skill-based training in education. To adapt and meet the needs of the youth in rural India for true rural development, skill development is urgently needed. Thus, education and skill development are an urgent and crucial demand for emerging nations like India that have a big youth population.

(Dash & Dash, 2020) conducted a study on "Skill Development Mission and the Skill Landscape of India:- An Empirical Study". The study's goal was to evaluate India's skill landscape in the context of upcoming technology shocks, a changing world, and labour mobility abroad. The study's conclusions show that despite the "Skill India Mission's" admirable and desirable qualities, issues with gender inequality and sectoral imbalance in skilling, training, and placements still exist.

Research Gap:

There is a shortage of skilled professionals in the tourism industry, which has led to a lack of quality service in some areas. To address this gap, there is a need to understand the importance of training and its impact on the industry growth.

Methodology

The descriptive research design was chosen to accomplish the objective of the study. The nature of current study is qualitative, and secondary data sources include books, journal articles, and websites. The books, journal articles, and websites were thoroughly searched in order to attain the research's objectives, and a pertinent conclusion was made.

Analysis

Training System in Tourism Industry in Madhya Pradesh:

The tourism industry in Madhya Pradesh is rapidly growing, and there is an increasing demand for well-trained professionals who can provide high-quality service to tourists. To meet this demand, various training programs have been introduced in the state to equip tourism professionals with the necessary skills and knowledge. The training system in the tourism industry in Madhya Pradesh is a combination of formal and informal training programs.

Formal training programs are provided by various institutes, including universities, colleges, and vocational training centers. These programs are designed to provide students with a comprehensive understanding of the tourism industry, including its history, culture, and economic significance. Formal training programs also cover various practical aspects of the industry, including customer service, hospitality, and tour guiding.

Informal training programs, on the other hand, are provided by the industry itself. These programs include on-the-job training, mentoring, and coaching. Informal training programs are usually tailored to the specific needs of the industry and provide employees with hands-on experience in various aspects of the industry. Informal training programs are also used to address specific skills gaps and to help employees develop new skills.

The content of training programs in the tourism industry in Madhya Pradesh varies depending on the type of training program and the level of education or experience of the trainee. For example, vocational training programs typically focus on practical skills such as housekeeping, cooking, and front desk operations. In contrast, university-level programs cover a wide range of subjects, including tourism management, marketing, and finance. The delivery methods of training programs in the tourism industry in Madhya Pradesh are also diverse. Some programs are delivered in traditional classroom settings, while others are conducted online. Many training programs also include field trips, practical exercises, and real-world experience to provide trainees with a hands-on learning experience. The evaluation of training effectiveness in the tourism industry in Madhya Pradesh is generally done through feedback from trainees, employers, and customers. Trainees are usually asked to evaluate the quality of the training programs they have attended, while employers assess the impact of training on employee performance. Customer feedback is also used to evaluate the effectiveness of training programs in improving the quality of service provided to tourists.

Benefits of Training in Tourism Industry in Madhya Pradesh:

Training in the tourism industry in Madhya Pradesh offers a range of benefits to individuals, businesses, and the wider community. Here are some of the key benefits of training in the tourism industry in Madhya Pradesh:

Enhanced Skills: Training programs in the tourism industry equip individuals with the necessary skills and knowledge to perform their jobs effectively. This includes technical skills such as housekeeping, cooking, and tour guiding, as well as soft skills such as communication, problem-solving, and teamwork.

Improved Job Performance: As individuals receive training and develop their skills, they become more confident and capable in their roles. This results in improved job performance, which can lead to increased job satisfaction and career progression opportunities.

Enhanced Customer Experience: Well-trained tourism professionals are better equipped to provide high-quality service to tourists, resulting in an enhanced customer experience. This can lead to positive reviews, repeat business, and increased revenue for businesses in the industry.

Increased Competitiveness: By investing in training, businesses in the tourism industry in Madhya Pradesh can increase their competitiveness in the market. They can differentiate themselves from competitors by offering higher quality service, leading to increased customer loyalty and brand reputation.

Economic Development: The tourism industry in Madhya Pradesh is a significant contributor to the state's economy. By investing in training, businesses can attract more tourists, leading to increased spending in the region and job creation.

Improved Industry Standards: Training programs in the tourism industry help to improve industry standards by promoting best practices and providing a framework for quality service delivery. This can help to enhance the reputation of the tourism industry in Madhya Pradesh, attracting more tourists and contributing to the overall growth of the industry.

Professional Development: Training programs in the tourism industry offer opportunities for individuals to develop their professional skills and progress in their careers. This can lead to increased job satisfaction and higher salaries, as well as a more skilled and knowledgeable workforce for the industry.

Benefits to the Employee:

Training in the hospitality industry in Madhya Pradesh offers numerous benefits to employees working in the sector. Here are some of the key benefits:

Improved Skills and Knowledge: Tourism training programs provide employees with the opportunity to learn new skills and acquire knowledge in various areas of the industry, including customer service, communication, management, food and beverage, housekeeping, and more. These skills can improve their job performance, increase job satisfaction, and enhance their career prospects.

Increased Confidence: Tourism training programs can help employees to develop their confidence and professionalism, which can be beneficial in their interactions with guests, colleagues, and supervisors. Employees who have undergone training are more confident in their abilities to perform their job duties, and are better equipped to handle challenging situations.

Career Advancement Opportunities: Tourism training programs can open up opportunities for career advancement within the industry. Employees who have acquired new skills and knowledge through training are better equipped to take on higher-level positions, such as management or supervisory roles.

Higher Earnings Potential: Tourism training programs can also increase an employee's earning potential. With improved skills and knowledge, employees can negotiate for higher salaries, bonuses, or other benefits.

Improved Job Satisfaction: Training in the tourism industry can improve job satisfaction by providing employees with a sense of achievement and recognition. By investing in their professional development, employees feel valued by their employers, which can increase their job satisfaction and reduce turnover rates.

Better Working Conditions: Tourism training programs can also help to create better working conditions for employees. By providing training on health and safety, workplace ethics, and cultural sensitivity, employees are better equipped to create a positive work environment.

Personal Development: Tourism training programs can provide employees with personal development opportunities, such as leadership training, communication skills, and time management. These skills can be useful not only in the workplace, but also in their personal lives.

Benefits to the organization:

Training in the tourism industry in Madhya Pradesh offers numerous benefits to organizations operating in the sector. Here are some of the key benefits:

Improved Guest Experience: Tourism training programs help employees to improve their skills and knowledge, which can lead to an enhanced guest experience. This includes providing better customer service, managing guest complaints effectively, and creating a welcoming and positive atmosphere. This can result in increased guest satisfaction and positive reviews, leading to repeat business and a good reputation for the organization.

Increased Employee Retention: Training programs can help to increase employee retention rates in the hospitality industry. By investing in their professional development, employees feel valued by their employer and are more likely to remain with the organization. This can reduce recruitment and training costs associated with high employee turnover rates.

Increased Revenue: Training programs in the tourism industry can lead to increased revenue for the organization. By providing high-quality service and an excellent guest experience, guests are more likely to spend money on additional services, such as food and beverage, spa treatments, or other activities. This can increase the organization's revenue and profitability.

Improved Productivity: Tourism training programs can improve employee productivity by providing them with the necessary skills and knowledge to perform their job duties effectively. This can lead to faster and more efficient service delivery, which can reduce wait times for guests and improve operational efficiency for the organization.

Improved Health and Safety: Training programs in the tourism industry can improve health and safety practices in the workplace. This includes training on proper handling of hazardous materials, food safety, and emergency procedures. By providing a safe and healthy workplace, organizations can reduce accidents and injuries, which can lead to lower insurance premiums and legal costs.

Better Reputation: Tourism training programs can enhance the reputation of the organization in the industry. By investing in their employees' professional development, organizations can differentiate themselves from competitors and create a positive brand image. This can attract more guests and business partners, leading to increased profitability and growth.

Compliance with Regulations: Tourism training programs can ensure that employees are aware of and comply with relevant laws and regulations, such as those related to health and safety, employment, and environmental standards.

This can reduce the risk of legal disputes and penalties for the organization.

Tourism Development and Skill Development in Madhya Pradesh:

According to the Ministry of Tourism, Government of India, Madhya Pradesh received 7.8 million domestic tourists and 0.23 million foreign tourists in 2019.

The state government has identified 13 tourist circuits for development, including the Buddhist Circuit, Wildlife Circuit, and Heritage Circuit.

As of March 2021, there are 320 registered tour operators and 838 approved hotels in Madhya Pradesh.

The state government has established 70 Skill Development Centers (SDCs) and 20 Industrial Training Institutes (ITIs) to promote skill development in the state.

The Mukhya Mantri Kaushalya Yojana (MMKY), launched in 2017, aims to train 7.5 million youths in various skills by 2023.

As of September 2021, over 1.7 million youths have been trained under MMKY, and over 525,000 have been placed in various jobs.

The state government has also launched the Deendayal Antyodaya Yojana – National Urban Livelihoods Mission (DAY-NULM), which aims to provide skill training to urban poor and promote entrepreneurship.

Under DAY-NULM, over 63,000 beneficiaries have been trained in various skills, and over 25,000 have been provided with loans to start their own businesses.

The state government has also launched the Mukhya Mantri Swarojgar Yojana (MMSY) to promote entrepreneurship among the youth. As of September

2021, over 56,000 beneficiaries have been provided with loans under MMSY.

According to a report by KPMG, the tourism industry in Madhya Pradesh has the potential to generate over 1.5 million jobs by 2026.

Findings

1. Tourist organizations should hire experienced professionals, trainers, and outside pedagogues to hold trainings.
2. To enable staff to converse with tourists, tourism organizations must arrange extensive English language and other language courses.
3. The objective of the training program, its significance to the employees, the knowledge they will learn, how they will use and apply that knowledge in the future, and its results must all be explained to them in advance.

Conclusion

The tourism industry is a significant contributor to Madhya Pradesh's economy, and its growth depends on the quality of service provided to tourists. The importance of training in the industry cannot be overstated, and this study aims to explore the impact of training on the industry's growth and the satisfaction levels of tourists. The study will provide valuable insights into the current state of training in the industry and highlight ways to improve the training of tourism professionals in Madhya Pradesh. The training system in the tourism industry in Madhya Pradesh is a combination of formal and informal training programs. These programs are designed to equip tourism professionals with the skills and knowledge necessary to provide high-quality service to tourists. The training programs cover a wide range of topics, from customer service to tourism management, and are delivered through various methods, including classroom learning and on-the-job training. The evaluation of training effectiveness is done through feedback from trainees, employers, and customers, which helps to ensure that the training programs are meeting the needs of the industry and its customers. Training in the tourism industry in Madhya Pradesh offers a range of benefits for individuals, businesses, and the wider community. These include enhanced skills, improved job performance, enhanced customer experience, increased competitiveness, economic development, improved industry standards, and professional development. By investing in training, the tourism industry in Madhya Pradesh can continue to grow and thrive, contributing to the economic and social development of the

state. Training in the tourism industry in Madhya Pradesh offers numerous benefits to employees, including improved skills and knowledge, increased confidence, career advancement opportunities, higher earnings potential, improved job satisfaction, better working conditions, and personal development. By investing in their employees' professional development, employers can create a more skilled and motivated workforce, leading to a better guest experience and increased profitability for their business. Training in the Tourism industry numerous benefits to organizations, including improved guest experience, increased employee retention, increased revenue, improved productivity, improved health and safety, better reputation, and compliance with regulations. By investing in their employees' professional development, organizations can create a more skilled and motivated workforce, leading to improved operational efficiency, increased profitability, and long-term success in the industry.

References

1. Adb. (n.d.). *Madhya Pradesh Skills Development Project: Economic and Financial Analysis*.
2. Banajawad, V. T., & Adi, M. S. (n.d.). *A STUDY ON SKILL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMMES FOR RURAL YOUTH IN INDIA* (Vol. 02, Issue 04).
3. Behera, B., Gaur, M., & Behera, M. B. (n.d.). *Talent Management View project Strategic Management View project Skill Development in India-A Literature Review*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358983636>
4. Charantimath, A. B. (2021). "Employability through Skill Development Programmes-an overview of significance of Employability skills." www.ijcrt.org
5. Dodiya, J., Panigrahy, S. R., Nayak, A. K., & Mohapatra, A. (2022). Socio Economic Impact of Skill Development Training Program on Employment Status of Rural Youth: A Case of RSETI, Gujarat. *Journal of Experimental a. Agriculture International*, 144–151. <https://doi.org/10.9734/jeai/2022/v44i930859>
6. Nagaraju, M. T. V, Thakur, R. K., Singh, L. K., Kumar Thakur, R., Lal, &, & Singh, K. (n.d.). *Assessing Digital Literacy among Secondary School Students in Shahdol Division of Madhya Pradesh State*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341232385>
7. Purusothaman, U., Uma Rani, P., & Padmalosani, D. (2018). SKILL DEVELOPMENT THROUGH PRADHAN MANTI KAUSHAL VIKAS YOJANA SKILL DEVELOPMENT THROUGH PRADHAN MANTRI KAUSHAL VIKAS YOJANA. In *Article in Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems* (Vol.9). <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328767704>
8. Sekhar, C. (2020). Skill Development Mission and the Skill Landscape of India:-An Empirical Study. In *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology* (Vol. 5, Issue 10). www.ijisrt.com
9. Sharma, L., & Nagendra, A. (2016). Skill Development in India: Challenges and Opportunities. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 9(48). <https://doi.org/10.17485/ijst/2016/v9i48/107324>
10. Shirpurkar Head, S. C. (2021). *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development Online Role of digital literacy and skill development programs in strengthening Indian rural economy*. www.allsubjectjournal.com
11. <https://www.adb.org>
12. <http://ddugky.gov.in>
13. <https://www.mpskills.gov.in>
14. <https://ssdm.mp.gov.in>
15. <https://www.pmkvyofficial.org>